

Automating Terminal Airspace Vectoring: A Machine-Assisted Approach for Sequencing, Spacing and Merging of Arrival Flights

Imen Dhief, Zhi Jun Lim, Hao Jiang, Duc-Thinh Pham and Sameer Alam
Air Traffic Management Research Institute Nanyang Technological University, Singapore

Abstract—The increasing volume of global air traffic presents significant operational challenges, particularly within the Terminal Maneuvering Airspace (TMA), where Air Traffic Controllers (ATCs) must efficiently manage converging and diverging traffic flows. While automation has enhanced various aspects of Air Traffic Management (ATM), existing systems primarily assist in monitoring and sequencing aircraft without fully supporting ATCs in vectoring operations. In high-density TMAs, ATCs frequently apply shortcuts and elongations to sequence and merge flights while maintaining separation standards. However, the tactical and unstructured nature of vectoring often leads to over-vectoring, prolonged flight times, and increased TMA congestion.

This paper proposes a novel sequencing, spacing, and merging methodology based on simulated annealing optimization, automating vectoring decisions by translating historical flight trajectories into conflict-free, optimized structured paths. The approach minimizes time spent in the arrival phase while integrating shortcut and elongation maneuvers, ensuring structured sequencing and safe aircraft spacing across multiple STAR routes. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed methodology enables 95% of flights to reach the Initial Approach Fix (IAF) earlier than their original arrival times, significantly reducing overall travel times while preserving safe separation. The findings confirm that the model reduces daily arrival flight time by more than four hours, yielding substantial operational efficiency gains and improving traffic flow management in congested TMAs.

Keywords—Air Traffic Management, Terminal Maneuvering Airspace, Sequencing, Spacing and Merging, Automate Vectoring, Simulated Annealing

I. INTRODUCTION

The continuous growth of global air traffic presents significant operational challenges, particularly within the Terminal Maneuvering Airspace (TMA)—a critical bottleneck in the aviation system. The TMA serves as the transition airspace between en-route operations and airport surface traffic management, accommodating high-density, converging, and diverging air traffic streams. Managing the safe, efficient, and timely flow of aircraft within this complex environment has long been a demanding task for air traffic controllers (ATCs). To enhance efficiency and reduce workload, automation has become an integral component of Air Traffic Management (ATM), providing essential support in handling the growing complexity of TMA traffic flow.

Advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and data analytics have significantly enhanced ATC automation, optimizing various aspects of ATM operations. Within the TMA, automation has led to improvements through systems such as the Arrival/Departure Manager

(AMAN/DMAN), Extended Arrival Manager, and Integrated Arrival/Departure (IAD) systems, all of which assist ATCs in sequencing aircraft and increasing runway throughput.

Despite advancements in automation, ATCs remain essential in dynamically managing flights within the TMA. Under low-traffic conditions, controllers frequently issue shortcut clearances, allowing aircraft to deviate from Standard Terminal Arrival Routes (STARs) for a more direct approach to the runway. However, in high-traffic scenarios, ATCs rely on radar vectoring and holding patterns to maintain safe separation and sequencing compliance. The real-time, unpredictable nature of vectoring often leads to excessive maneuvering and extended flight durations, increasing congestion within the TMA.

Moreover, the tactical and unstructured nature of these vectoring decisions makes it challenging for automation systems to interpret ATC decision-making processes and effectively assist in air traffic control tasks [1]. For instance, systems such as the Digital Tower Assistant (DiTA) [2] have been introduced to monitor approach and landing phases, however, their functionality is limited to tracking aircraft closely following STARs without adapting vectoring decisions in response to evolving traffic dynamics.

Effective TMA traffic management requires sophisticated vectoring strategies to ensure safe and efficient aircraft sequencing. This is particularly relevant in high-density TMAs, such as Singapore Changi Airport, where frequent vectoring and holding patterns are observed [3]. Research has demonstrated a direct correlation between TMA vectoring and increased operational complexity, leading to higher controller workload [4]. As traffic volumes continue to rise, these challenges will only intensify. A machine-assisted vectoring system capable of managing a portion of the ATC workload is essential to maintaining efficiency. Crucially, such a system must go beyond simple flight monitoring and incorporate re-routing instructions, including shortcuts and elongations, based on the prevailing traffic situation.

To address these challenges, this paper introduces a novel trajectory-based optimization methodology for sequencing, spacing and merging arrival flights by automating ATC vectoring strategies. The concept diagram of our proposed methodology is highlighted in figure 1. The objective is to translate historical flight trajectories into a set of conflict-free, structured trajectories, effectively capturing the decision-making process of human controllers in precise, actionable steps. Specifically, this work aims to develop automated re-routing strategies that

replace traditional vectoring techniques, offering a structured and predictable approach to traffic management. By improving aircraft spacing and sequencing, the proposed methodology enhances efficiency and organization within the TMA.

Figure 1: Conceptual representation of the proposed vectoring approach, comparing it to the original scenario for optimizing arrival trajectories within a STAR. The structured method (top) integrates shortcut and elongation maneuvers to reduce travel time while maintaining sequencing and spacing. In contrast, the original scenario (bottom figure) relies on unstructured, tactical vectoring decisions.

Additionally, the optimized trajectories provide a robust dataset for training AI-driven ATC support systems, enabling automation-assisted air traffic management. The proposed methodology also lays the groundwork for future modernization efforts, such as Trajectory-Based Operations (TBO). By promoting predictable flight paths, this approach reduces reliance on open-loop vectoring, facilitating the implementation of 4D trajectory negotiation and more efficient airspace management.

Building upon the foundational work presented in [5], the current research offers significant advancements in several key areas. Specifically, the present contribution includes the following enhancements:

- **Real-World Data Application:** Unlike the previous study [5], which relied on simulated data, this work utilizes real-world historical flight trajectory data. This shift to authentic operational data provides a more realistic and robust evaluation of the proposed methodology, enhancing its applicability to real-world ATM scenarios.

- **System-Level Applicability and Instruction Set Expansion:** While [5] focused on traffic along a single STAR route and considered only elongation instructions, the methodology presented here is designed for system-level application, encompassing all STAR routes within the TMA simultaneously. This broader scope enables a comprehensive and integrated optimization of traffic flow across the entire airspace. Furthermore, this work expands the instruction set to include

both elongation and shortcut instructions, providing greater flexibility and efficiency in traffic management.

- **Conflict-Free Trajectories:** A key distinction from [5] lies in the handling of potential conflicts. Whereas the earlier work treated conflicts as relaxed constraints, the present model explicitly enforces conflict avoidance. The resulting automated trajectories are guaranteed to be conflict-free, ensuring a higher level of safety in the optimized traffic flow.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II provides a literature review of existing methods for managing arrival traffic. Section III outlines the objectives and motivation of this study. Section IV presents the problem formulation for the trajectory vectoring approach, followed by Section V, which details the proposed methodology. Section VI discusses the computational results, and finally, Section VII summarizes the key findings and conclusions.

II. RELATED WORKS

This work addresses the critical challenge of flight spacing and sequencing of arrival flights. While Arrival Management (AMAN) systems effectively sequence aircraft for runway landings based on their estimated times of arrival (ETAs), translating this sequence into efficient arrival operations remains a significant challenge. Upon entering the TMA, an aircraft's ETA is determined and integrated into the runway sequence, and the corresponding time allocation within the TMA is calculated. ATC is then responsible for managing each flight from TMA entry to runway landing according to this pre-computed sequence. To achieve this, controllers rely heavily on radar vectoring, employing both elongations and shortcuts to maintain the desired arrival sequence. However, within the complex and often congested TMA environment, this reliance on vectoring frequently results in delays, inefficiencies, and increased controller workload. To support controllers in this challenging environment, numerous decision-support tools have been proposed in the literature. These approaches can be broadly categorized into three main areas.

- **Data-Driven Prediction Models:** Several studies have explored the use of data-driven prediction models to forecast arrival times [6], [7] and delays [8] within the TMA. These predictive capabilities enable proactive sequencing strategies, such as en-route speed control [3], facilitated by the extended look-ahead horizon provided by Extended-AMAN systems. However, accurately predicting TMA transit times remains a significant challenge due to the inherently complex and tactical nature of flight trajectories within this airspace. While en-route speed control has proven effective in reducing the need for in-TMA rerouting, residual delays often persist due to the inherent inaccuracies of current prediction models [3].

- **Continuous Descent Operations (CDOs):** CDOs offer another promising avenue for enhancing TMA efficiency. CDOs allow aircraft to descend continuously using minimal engine thrust and a low-drag configuration, facilitated through coordinated airspace and procedure design in conjunction with ATC [9]. Research has consistently demonstrated the substantial benefits of CDOs in reducing fuel consumption, emissions, and noise during descent [10], [11]. However, the implementation of CDOs presents challenges. These procedures

typically require larger separation buffers between arriving aircraft compared to conventional step-descent operations. This increased separation is necessary as ATC must closely monitor continuous descent trajectories to ensure conflict avoidance and maintain safe operations, potentially impacting airport capacity utilization [12]. Consequently, while CDOs can be effectively implemented at airports with relatively low traffic density, such as during late-night or early-morning periods, their applicability in busy TMAs remains limited [13], [14].

Fixed and Dynamic Route Structures: Fixed structure-based approaches have also been investigated to optimize flight trajectories within the TMA. Some studies rely on predefined route structures imposed by STAR procedures. For example, Zhang et al. [15] present an optimization model for routing flights within the Singapore TMA, utilizing speed adjustments and holding patterns as key decision variables. The proposed model, tested with simulated data, aims to minimize flight time within the TMA while optimizing runway throughput. However, real-world TMA flight data analysis reveals that ATCs frequently deviate from predefined STARS to manage traffic more efficiently through elongations and shortcut maneuvers. This deviation highlights the need for a more adaptive approach that accounts for real-world vectoring strategies. Furthermore, speed control in the TMA is highly constrained by the speed restrictions imposed by the Aeronautical Information Publication (AIP) at each STAR waypoint, limiting its effectiveness as a primary traffic management tool. Other studies have explored more sophisticated, dynamic route structures as alternatives to traditional vectoring within the TMA. A prominent example is the Point Merge System (PMS), introduced by the EUROCONTROL Experimental Centre (EEC) in 2006 [16]. Currently deployed at 56 airports across 23 countries, PMS has been the subject of extensive research, with numerous studies examining its implementation and operational effectiveness [17], [18]. Another dynamic routing approach is the Trombone system, a Performance-Based Navigation (PBN)-based arrival procedure that has demonstrated efficacy in efficiently absorbing delays within the TMA [19]. While these topologies typically require a radius of 25 to 40 nautical miles (NM) from the airport reference point, this spatial requirement poses a significant challenge for airspaces such as the Singapore TMA. A substantial portion of the airspace surrounding Singapore falls under the jurisdiction of neighboring countries, limiting the adoption of standard PMS and Trombone systems.

III. OBJECTIVE AND MOTIVATION

In response to the challenges outlined above, this paper proposes an optimization model to transform historical flight arrival trajectories into a dynamic and structured arrival routing system, inspired by the work presented in [5]. The primary objective is to efficiently space, sequence, and merge arrival flights through an organized vectoring strategy that incorporates both elongation and shortcut instructions.

The proposed route structure leverages key features extracted from historical flight data, including arrival travel times, assigned STARS, and speed and altitude profiles at each STAR waypoint. By integrating these elements, the approach aims

to generate optimized, conflict-free trajectories that enhance spacing and merging efficiency, ensuring adherence to ATC decisions while maintaining operational safety.

The primary motivation of this work is to lay the groundwork for an ATC assistant system capable of monitoring and managing flight operations within the TMA, thereby reducing ATC workload. This system should be designed to replicate ATC decision-making processes and control strategies, particularly in sequencing, spacing and merging TMA traffic. By leveraging historical flight data, our objective is to translate radar-vectoring strategies employed by ATC into a structured set of instructions that can be implemented by an intelligent assistant system.

Another key motivation is to promote the implementation of a flexible STAR configuration within the TMA, tailored to varying traffic levels. This flexibility is achieved by introducing additional metering fixes to accommodate vectoring maneuvers during periods of high traffic congestion or deactivating specific metering fixes to facilitate shortcuts when traffic levels are low. Such adaptability aims to enhance airspace utilization and improve overall traffic flow efficiency.

Lastly, the complexity of TMA traffic management, shaped by ATC decisions, underscores the need for a structured yet adaptable routing framework. A well-organized and flexible route structure within the TMA can significantly reduce operational uncertainties, laying the foundation for more reliable predictive models. These models will enable more accurate forecasting of aircraft sequencing and spacing, leading to improved efficiency and optimized runway throughput.

IV. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The TMA is the controlled airspace surrounding an airport, with its coverage defined by airspace regulations that vary across different airports. The structure of each TMA is based on Standard Terminal Arrival Routes (STARs) and Standard Instrument Departures (SIDs), as specified in the respective Aeronautical Information Publication (AIP). STARs and SIDs consist of predefined waypoint sequences that guide arriving and departing aircraft along designated flight paths. These structured procedures incorporate altitude and speed constraints to ensure orderly and efficient traffic flow.

It is important to note that STARs and SIDs often extend beyond the boundaries of the TMA. For instance, STARs can begin at a radius of up to 200 nautical miles (NM) from the airport, where aircraft initiate their descent phase, whereas the TMA itself typically covers a radius of around 50 NM.

Various operational challenges—such as traffic congestion, adverse weather conditions, or temporary runway unavailability—frequently necessitate deviations from standard routes. In such cases, ATCs implement alternative traffic management strategies, including vectoring and holding maneuvers. Vectoring involves providing aircraft with specific heading instructions to maintain safe separation and optimize sequencing, while holding requires aircraft to follow circular patterns to absorb arrival delays and regulate traffic flow within the TMA.

This study primarily focuses on arrival flights, as they are more susceptible to in-flight vectoring and rerouting maneuvers—key contributors to congestion within the TMA.

Moreover, considering the typical altitude separation between STARs and SIDs, managing arrival and departure trajectories independently is a practical and safe operational assumption. This separation minimizes conflicts between inbound and outbound traffic, enabling more precise control over arrival flows while ensuring that departure operations remain unaffected.

The approach presented in this paper introduces an optimization model that leverages historical flight data to generate new, optimized descent-phase trajectories while adhering to time and safety constraints. The trajectories considered in this study extend beyond the TMA boundaries and include arrival flights from the entry points of the STARs.

In actual operations, the transit time for each flight at the descent phase is determined by the optimal runway sequence issued by the Arrival Manager (AMAN) system. It is then the responsibility of ATC to manage how this time is distributed within the descent phase. Our proposed approach aims to support ATC in this task by generating optimized descent trajectories that comply with operational constraints, thereby enhancing efficiency and reducing unnecessary delays.

The sequencing of flights at the runway is beyond the scope of this study. Consequently, the flight sequence derived from historical data remains unchanged. However, we argue that ATC vectoring measures often lead to inefficiencies due to the difficulty in accurately estimating the time required for an aircraft to fly a deviated trajectory. Therefore, while maintaining the original flight sequence, we propose that an optimization model can generate more efficient trajectories, reducing overall flight time and minimizing delays while ensuring compliance with sequencing and spacing constraints.

Historical flight trajectory data are analyzed by extracting information from the point of STAR entry to STAR exit. These data provide key insights into how flights are managed during the descent phase, capturing specific operational characteristics. Based on this information, flights are first categorized into shortcut or elongation maneuvers, reflecting the different vectoring strategies employed by ATC. Additionally, detailed data at each STAR metering fix are extracted and utilized as input parameters for the optimization model, ensuring that the generated trajectories adhere to operational constraints.

V. METHODOLOGY

This study explores an optimization model designed to generate optimal, conflict-free descent trajectories that adhere to spacing and sequencing constraints, ensuring safe and efficient air traffic operations. The methodology framework, illustrated in Figure 2, outlines the key components involved in developing our model. It incorporates multiple data sources, including historical ADS-B data, airspace data, and the BADA performance model, which collectively provide a comprehensive foundation for trajectory optimization.

The process begins with a preprocessing phase, where historical flight data is mapped to the corresponding STARs using airspace data as a reference framework for aligning historical trajectories. Key operational parameters, such as travel time, speed, and altitude at STAR waypoints, are then extracted. These parameters are incorporated into the optimization model to accurately reflect real-world operational constraints in the

generated trajectories. Furthermore, they serve as the foundation for developing vectoring strategies that ensure compliance with sequencing constraints.

As the optimization model iteratively generates new flight trajectories, it is essential to compute the time required for each flight to traverse the optimized trajectory. This is achieved through the implementation of a point mass model, which leverages the BADA performance model to ensure accuracy in trajectory time estimation.

The final output of the model is a set of optimized, conflict-free descent trajectories. To evaluate the effectiveness of these trajectories, a comparative assessment is conducted, analyzing the efficiency of optimized trajectories relative to historical ones in terms of flight delays and time spent within the TMA.

A. Data Source

The current study utilizes three primary data sources:

Historical ADS-B dataset provides comprehensive information on aircraft trajectories, including positional data (latitude, longitude, and altitude), heading, speed, and timestamps. It also includes crucial flight information such as aircraft type, which is essential for generating accurate flight profiles and ensuring safe separation between optimized trajectories. The ADS-B data utilized in this study represents one full day of flight traffic sourced from Flightradar24.

The airspace data utilized in this study is extracted from the AIP manual. It provides a detailed representation of the airway structure, including the precise coordinates of STAR waypoints. Additionally, this dataset encompasses critical operational constraints at STAR waypoints, such as altitude restrictions, speed limitations, and designated holding patterns.

The Base of Aircraft Data (BADA) is an aircraft performance model developed by EUROCONTROL [20]. It consists of a collection of ASCII files containing essential performance parameters and operational coefficients for 295 different aircraft types. These parameters facilitate the computation of key flight dynamics, including thrust, drag, and fuel flow, while also defining nominal cruise, climb, and descent speeds. In this study, the BADA model is employed to simulate descent trajectories, providing accurate estimations flight timings at STARs waypoints. This ensures that the generated trajectories align with real-world aircraft performance characteristics.

B. Data Preprocessing

The data pre-processing phase is essential for analyzing historical flight data and extracting trajectory features that support the proposed methodology. This phase ensures data reliability and enhances the accuracy of the optimization model by refining and structuring the input data.

The first step in pre-processing involves filtering trajectories to remove flights with incomplete or inconsistent data. For instance, trajectories that are truncated at high altitudes or contain data points separated by more than 10 nautical miles (NM) are excluded. Additionally, flights that do not align with any STARs or that enter STARs at intermediate waypoints are also removed. Since the optimization model operates on flights from the entry waypoint of STARs, partially recorded trajectories cannot be processed at this stage.

Figure 2: Optimization framework for automated sequencing, spacing, and merging of arrival flights, covering the entire trajectory optimization process from data pre-processing to conflict-free trajectory generation. It integrates ADS-B data, airspace constraints, and the BADA model to compute optimized flight paths using shortcut and elongation maneuvers while ensuring conflict avoidance and adherence to heading constraints. Effectiveness is evaluated based on its ability to space, merge, and sequence flights, as well as reduce time spent in STARs.

Following this filtering process, Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) is employed to map each historical trajectory to its closest corresponding STAR. DTW is particularly suitable for this task as it effectively computes the distance between two time series with potentially different lengths or sampling rates, accommodating variations in flight paths and data recording frequencies. To further refine the mapping process and identify corresponding data points at each STAR waypoint, the Haversine distance metric is utilized. This metric is commonly employed in aviation and geospatial applications due to its accuracy in calculating distances between two points on a sphere, such as the Earth. By considering the Earth's curvature, the Haversine formula provides more precise distance calculations over long distances compared to Euclidean distance, making it well-suited for determining the closest trajectory points to each STAR waypoint. Mapping trajectory points to different STAR waypoints enables the computation of flight travel time from the moment a flight joins the STAR until it reaches the Initial Approach Fix (IAF) (last waypoint of the STAR). By

comparing these actual travel times to the nominal duration expected if the aircraft were to strictly follow the STAR, flights can be classified into two categories: those that have taken shortcuts and those that have undergone elongation maneuvers.

C. Optimization problem formulation

Consider an arriving flight f^i entering the initial waypoint of a STAR route, with an expected arrival at the final approach fix at time t_{IAF}^i . If f^i is anticipated to experience a delay of duration d_{fi} during its descent phase, the goal is to generate a deviated trajectory that adjusts the flight path around the STAR route, ensuring that f^i reaches the final approach fix at $t_e^i + d_{fi}$. Conversely, if the flight is expected to take a shortcut reducing its descent time by s_{fi} , the objective is to strategically remove one or more STAR waypoints to facilitate the required time reduction while maintaining operational constraints. The considered problem is formulated as follows.

a) *Input data:* Consider a set of n arrival flights, denoted as $\mathcal{F} = \{f^1, f^2, \dots, f^n\}$, approaching the subject airport. For each flight f^i , the following input data is utilized:

- **STAR Route:** The assigned STAR for flight f^i , denoted as $STAR^i$, comprises a sequence of m waypoints, represented as (w_j) where $j \in \{1 \cdots m\}$.
- **STAR Entry Time:** The time at which flight f^i enters the STAR, denoted as t_e^i .
- **IAF Arrival Time:** The assigned time of arrival at the IAF for flight f^i , denoted as (t_{IAF}^i) . This information is extracted from historical flight data.
- **Nominal Time in the STAR:** The estimated travel time for flight f^i when strictly following the assigned STAR route, denoted as $t_{Nominal}^i$. This value is derived using the BADA performance model.
- **Vectoring Instruction:** Indicates whether a shortcut (S^i) or an elongation (E^i) maneuver is applied to flight f^i .
- **True Airspeed Profile:** The true airspeed (TAS) of flight f^i at each STAR waypoint (w_j), denoted as $(TAS_{w_j}^i)$ for $j \in \{1 \cdots m\}$.
- **Altitude Profile:** The altitude of flight f^i at each STAR waypoint (w_j), denoted as $(ALT_{w_j}^i)$ for $j \in \{1 \cdots m\}$.

b) *Decision variable:* The decision variables within the optimization model are contingent upon the specific vectoring instruction (elongation or shortcut) applied to each flight.

- **Trajectory Elongation:** For elongation maneuvers, a set of trajectory deviation angles, denoted as (α_i) for $i \in [1..m]$, is introduced. Each α_i represents the assigned deviation angle at waypoint w_i along the STAR route, with m representing the total number of waypoints. To accurately reflect the trajectory vectoring strategies implemented by air traffic controllers and to facilitate the administration of vectoring maneuvers, the deviation angle α_i is modeled as a discrete variable, constrained to the range of $[-30^\circ, +30^\circ]$ with increments of 5° . These deviations result in the insertion of additional waypoints between each pair of consecutive waypoints on the original STAR route, thereby increasing the total number of waypoints in the resulting trajectory.
- **Trajectory Shortcutting:** For shortcutting maneuvers, the approach involves the removal of one or more waypoints along the STAR route. The waypoints are selected for removal through a random process, ensuring that the first and last waypoints of the STAR are retained. This random elimination of intermediate waypoints serves to shorten the trajectory, thereby reducing flight time and improving overall efficiency, while still maintaining the integrity of the initial and final segments of the route.

c) *Constraints:* In the current study, two primary constraints are considered:

- **Maximum Trajectory Deviation:** Based on input from subject matter experts, the maximum allowable deviation for the trajectory is capped at 30° . As such, the deviation angle α_i at each waypoint w_i must satisfy the following condition:

$$|\alpha_i| \leq \alpha_{max}, \forall i \in \{1, \cdots, m\}, \text{ where } \alpha_{max} = 30^\circ$$

This constraint ensures that the trajectory deviation remains within acceptable bounds, as determined by expert recommendations.

- **Conflict Avoidance:** To ensure safe flight operations, the study incorporates conflict avoidance based on airspace structure. Specifically, potential conflicts are assumed to arise in the event of a separation violation, either along the route link or at the waypoint nodes. The required spatial separation between two successive flights within the TMA is set to 3 NM. This separation must be maintained at both the entry and exit nodes of each route segment. If no conflict is detected within the link, the separation is automatically ensured. The conflict detection method employed is similar to the one proposed by [8].

d) *Objective:* For each flight f^i , let $T_{Baseline}^{f^i}$ denote the baseline travel time along the STAR, representing the actual travel time extracted from historical data. It is defined as:

$$T_{Baseline}^{f^i} = t_{IAF}^{f^i} - t_e^{f^i}$$

where $t_{IAF}^{f^i}$ is the arrival time at the IAF, and $t_e^{f^i}$ is the flight's entry time into the STAR.

To accommodate the necessary rerouting for each flight trajectory, a vectoring strategy is applied, resulting in a new travel time $T_{new}^{f^i}$, which is computed using the point mass model. The objective is to ensure that this new travel time closely aligns with the historical baseline travel time. The deviation from the baseline for each flight is given by:

$$\delta^{f^i} = \left| T_{Baseline}^{f^i} - T_{new}^{f^i} \right|$$

To optimize overall system performance, the goal is to minimize the total deviation across all flights, expressed as:

$$\text{obj} = \min \left(\sum_{\forall f^i \in \mathcal{F}} \delta^{f^i} \right)$$

However, this formulation does not explicitly enforce that the new travel time $T_{new}^{f^i}$ remains less than or equal to the baseline travel time $T_{Baseline}^{f^i}$. To address this, a penalization factor w_1 is introduced to discourage excessive increases in travel time. The refined objective function is thus formulated as:

$$\text{obj} = \min \left(\sum_{\forall f^i \in \mathcal{F}} \delta^{f^i} + w_1 \cdot \max(0, T_{new}^{f^i} - T_{Baseline}^{f^i}) \right)$$

This formulation minimizes the cumulative deviation between baseline and new travel times while ensuring that the generated trajectories do not significantly exceed the baseline duration. Furthermore, to guarantee a conflict-free solution, an additional penalty term is introduced in the objective function. A high penalty weight, $w_0 = 10^3$, is assigned to the number of conflicts, denoted as Φ , ensuring that the algorithm converges toward a conflict-free solution. The final objective function is therefore given by:

$$\text{obj} = \min \left(w_0 \Phi + \sum_{\forall f^i \in \mathcal{F}} \delta^{f^i} + w_1 \cdot \max(0, T_{new}^{f^i} - T_{Baseline}^{f^i}) \right) \quad (1)$$

This formulation balances trajectory efficiency with conflict resolution, ensuring that rerouted flight paths maintain minimal deviation from historical travel times while adhering to safety constraints.

D. Simulated Annealing

Simulated Annealing (SA) is employed to solve the optimization problem presented in this work. SA is a meta-heuristic optimization algorithm inspired by the physical annealing process in materials science, where a material is heated and then gradually cooled to achieve a stable, low-energy state. The algorithm follows a similar principle, incorporating both a heating and cooling phase to explore and refine the solution space effectively. It begins with an initial random solution and a predefined control parameter, T , referred to as the temperature. At each iteration, a neighboring solution is generated along with its corresponding energy value (objective function), and the system transitions probabilistically between solutions. A higher temperature (T) encourages extensive exploration of the solution space, preventing premature convergence, while a lower temperature directs the system toward optimal solutions by refining the search.

The adaptation of SA to the current problem follows the approach described in [5], with modifications to incorporate the enhancements introduced in this work. The SA process is structured as follows:

- 1) **Search Space:** The search space consists of all possible flight trajectories for the set of flights \mathcal{F} .
- 2) **Energy Function:** The energy function is defined by the objective function of the optimization problem, as formulated in Equation 1.
- 3) **Neighbor Solution Generation:** A neighboring solution, \vec{x}_j , represents a local modification of the current solution, \vec{x}_i . The process of generating a neighbor solution involves two main steps:
 - a) *Flight Selection:* A flight is chosen for modification using the following heuristic:
 - A random value $p \in [0, 1]$ is generated from a uniform distribution.
 - If $p < 0.5$, the flight with the highest deviation between its baseline and new travel time is selected.
 - Otherwise, a random flight is chosen.
 - b) *Trajectory Modification:* Once the flight is selected, a new trajectory is generated based on the corresponding vectoring instruction:
 - If the vectoring instruction corresponds to a **shortcut**, one or more waypoints are randomly selected and removed from the assigned STAR. A maximum of three waypoints can be removed.
 - If the vectoring instruction corresponds to an **elongation**, two cases are considered:
 - If the new travel time is less than the baseline travel time, a new trajectory vectoring is randomly selected, ensuring that the total amount of vectoring (deviation in each segment) is greater than that of the current solution \vec{x}_i .
 - If the new travel time is greater than the baseline travel time, a new trajectory vectoring is randomly selected, ensuring that the amount of vectoring is less than that of the current solution \vec{x}_i .

- 4) **Acceptance Probability:** The probability of accepting a neighbor solution \vec{x}_j is computed using the Metropolis criterion:

$$P(\vec{x}_i \rightarrow \vec{x}_j) = e^{\frac{f(\vec{x}_i) - f(\vec{x}_j)}{T}}$$

where T is the current temperature, $f(\vec{x}_i)$ is the objective value of the current solution, and $f(\vec{x}_j)$ is the objective value of the neighbor solution. This probabilistic acceptance mechanism allows SA to escape local optima by occasionally accepting worse solutions.

- 5) **Temperature Cooling Schedule:** The temperature T is gradually decreased using a geometric cooling schedule:

$$T_i = \alpha \cdot T_{i-1}$$

where α is a cooling factor ($0 < \alpha < 1$), controlling the rate of temperature reduction.

- 6) **Termination Criterion:** The algorithm terminates when the temperature T falls below a predefined final temperature, T_f , defined as:

$$T_f = \beta \cdot T_{\text{init}}$$

where $\beta \ll 1$ and T_{init} is the initial temperature.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Use Case

The proposed methodology is applied to flights arriving at Singapore Changi Airport (ICAO: WSSS). The STAR procedures are sourced from the Singapore Aeronautical Information Publication (AIP) [21]. This study focuses on optimizing flight trajectories between STAR entry and exit points to improve arrival sequencing efficiency.

The experiments were conducted on May 3, 2024, for arrival flights to WSSS. Initially, 317 arriving flights were recorded. After filtering out flights with incomplete data, the dataset was reduced to 296 flights. Further refinement excluded flights that did not belong to any STAR or those that entered a STAR at an intermediate waypoint. The final dataset included 243 arrival flights, comprising 111 flights with elongated trajectories and 132 with shortcuts.

B. Spacing, Merging and Sequencing

The proposed methodology optimizes arrival flight trajectories while incorporating lateral adjustments to maintain the precomputed landing sequence at the runway. Each trajectory begins at a STAR entry waypoint and terminates at an IAF. In this study, flights from nine STARs are merged into two IAFs (BIPOP and NYLON), where they transition into the final approach phase. The merging process is governed by an optimization model designed to ensure smooth sequencing while minimizing disruptions.

a) Conflict Mitigation through Lateral Vectoring: Merging multiple flights in the same direction increases the likelihood of conflicts, particularly in high-traffic scenarios. To address this issue, lateral vectoring is implemented to maintain adequate flight spacing and ensure operational safety. Historical flight data, inherently conflict-free due to real-time ATC interventions, serve as a reference. However, when flights were simulated to strictly adhere to STARs without

vectoring, 42 conflicts were observed, underscoring the safety risks associated with rigid adherence to STARs in the absence of tactical adjustments.

The proposed optimization model generates conflict-free arrival trajectories by integrating a penalty mechanism that discourages conflicts, ensuring that the algorithm prioritizes safe aircraft spacing. Consequently, the model converges toward an optimized and operationally viable solution.

b) Evaluation of Flight Sequencing at Merging IAFs:

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed methodology in sequencing flights at the two merging IAFs, BIPOP and NYLON, the resulting flight sequence is compared with the initial sequence observed in historical data. The results, summarized in Table I, indicate that 172 flights pass through BIPOP, while 71 flights pass through NYLON. The sequencing process resulted in 23 flight swaps at BIPOP and 3 swaps at NYLON, demonstrating that sequence adjustments were made to optimise the order of arrival while minimizing the overall flight time in the STARs.

TABLE I. Initial Approach Fix Sequence Summary

IAF	Number of Flights	Number of Swaps	Spearman's Rank
BIPOP	172	23	0.999910
NYLON	71	3	0.999899

c) Sequence Reliability Assessment Using Spearman's Rank Correlation:

To evaluate the acceptability and reliability of the generated sequences, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient is employed as a metric. This statistical measure assesses the degree of similarity between two ranking orders [22], quantifying how closely the generated flight sequence preserves the original ATC-accepted order. A higher Spearman's rank correlation coefficient indicates a stronger alignment between the generated and historical sequences, making the proposed approach more suitable for operational implementation. As shown in Table I, both BIPOP and NYLON exhibit Spearman's rank correlation values close to 1 (0.999910 for BIPOP and 0.999899 for NYLON), indicating an extremely high level of agreement between the original and generated sequences. These results confirm that the proposed methodology effectively preserves the sequence of flights while making necessary optimizations. The minimal number of swaps at both IAFs, combined with near-perfect Spearman's rank correlation, suggests that the sequence adjustments are operationally feasible and align closely with human decision-making processes.

d) Distribution of Time Shifts in Arrival Sequences:

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of time shifts for all flights, showing how the proposed methodology affected arrival times at the IAF. The time shift is calculated as the difference between the initial and final arrival times at the IAF. A positive value indicates that a flight arrived earlier than in the original sequence, while a negative value represents a delayed arrival. The majority of flights cluster around zero, suggesting that their timing remained largely unchanged.

The distribution is right-skewed, confirming that 95% of the flights reached the IAF earlier than in the original sequence. The results further show that only 12 flights experienced a delay, with 11 flights delayed by less than two minutes and one flight delayed by six minutes. These minimal delays were

Figure 3: Histogram of time differences between initial (pre-process) and final (post-process) IAF arrival times. Flights with positive values (in blue) reached the IAF earlier than their historical sequence. The dashed black line represents the zero reference point.

necessary to enhance sequencing efficiency and reduce overall flight times within the STARs.

e) Analysis of Position Shifts in Flight Sequences:

Table II presents flights that experienced a shift of two or more positions compared to their initial sequence, along with their corresponding time differences, calculated as the initial time minus the original time at the IAF.

TABLE II. Flights with Two or More Position Shifts: The table displays initial and new ranks, position shifts, and time differences. A positive time difference indicates an earlier arrival at the IAF, while a negative value signifies a delay. The largest shift observed was four positions forward, leading to an arrival nearly 14 minutes earlier.

IAF	Flight	Initial Rank	New Rank	Shifts	Time Diff (min.)
BIPOP	1	72	69	3	11.05
BIPOP	2	68	71	3	-0.18
BIPOP	3	70	72	2	0.37
BIPOP	4	92	88	4	13.58
BIPOP	5	110	112	2	-5.57
BIPOP	6	143	141	2	10.87
BIPOP	7	150	148	2	5.72

The table shows that only seven flights experienced a shift of two or more positions, with the maximum shift being four positions forward, allowing the respective flight to reach the IAF nearly 14 minutes earlier than its original arrival time. Furthermore, the results indicate that three flights moved forward by up to three positions, while the remaining flights were shifted backward. Despite these adjustments, most flights arrived at the IAF earlier than in the original sequence. Only two flights experienced a delay, with the longest delay reaching nearly six minutes. These minor delays were necessary to achieve an optimized sequence while ensuring structured and efficient arrival flows.

C. Overall Trajectory Performance

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed trajectory generation methodology, Figure 4 compares historical flight trajectories (left) with optimized flight trajectories (right). The left panel illustrates the unstructured and varied nature of historical flight paths, where aircraft follow chaotic trajectories due to tactical ATC interventions such as vectoring and holding maneuvers. In contrast, the right panel presents the optimized

TABLE III. Comparison of the Baseline vs. Optimized Travel Time (TT) Statistics (in minutes)

STAR	Maximum TT		Minimum TT		Mean TT		STD TT		Total TT	
	Baseline	Optimized	Baseline	Optimized	Baseline	Optimized	Baseline	Optimized	Baseline	Optimized
ARAMA	43.97	39.13	16.98	15.72	24.72	23.90	5.83	5.83	1236.00	1195.00
ASUNA	35.63	35.63	13.70	13.08	21.35	20.88	6.03	6.28	256.20	250.56
BELVA	38.60	38.12	14.43	12.70	23.16	22.16	7.40	7.45	880.08	842.08
ELALO	44.57	44.53	21.38	20.65	29.10	28.07	6.38	7.17	407.40	392.98
TOMAN	45.03	40.77	17.87	17.05	26.24	25.09	7.83	7.45	839.68	802.88
MABAL	40.55	37.87	18.33	15.95	26.02	23.58	6.56	6.63	494.38	448.02
REPOV	40.98	29.88	12.75	9.97	19.82	18.41	6.19	5.39	416.22	386.61
TEBUN	34.13	33.50	15.28	14.38	22.01	21.27	5.86	5.67	286.13	276.51
UGEBO	47.08	41.57	15.97	14.93	24.64	23.41	7.21	6.65	1084.16	1030.04
Overall	47.08	44.53	12.75	9.97	24.12	22.97	6.59	6.50	5900.25	5624.68

Figure 4: Comparison of Historical and Optimized Flight Trajectories: The left panel shows unstructured historical flight paths with irregular trajectories due to tactical ATC vectoring, while the right panel illustrates optimized, structured trajectories along designated STARs. The proposed approach improves predictability, efficiency, and airspace utilization while ensuring compliance with ATC constraints.

trajectories, where aircraft follow structured, organized routes along designated STARs. The optimized approach streamlines arrival flows, minimizing trajectory dispersion while ensuring adherence to sequencing and spacing constraints. This structured routing enhances predictability, efficiency, and airspace utilization, while also reducing overall flight time, unnecessary deviations, fuel consumption, and emissions. The STAR labels in the right panel indicate specific entry points where aircraft are strategically assigned optimized routes, demonstrating the feasibility of integrating automation into ATC decision-making for improved arrival management.

The table III presents a comprehensive comparison between baseline travel times, derived from historical flight data, and optimized travel times generated by our proposed vectoring approach. This comparison provides critical insights into the

effectiveness of the proposed vectoring strategy and its impact on flight durations across various STARs. The table includes key statistics such as maximum, minimum, mean, and standard deviation (STD) of travel times, along with the total accumulated travel time across all flights for each STAR.

For most STARs, the difference between the minimum and maximum travel times exceeds 20 minutes, underscoring the significant influence of ATC interventions. These variations primarily result from vectoring maneuvers, which are implemented to regulate air traffic flow, maintain aircraft separation, and optimize arrival sequencing.

The variability in transit times is further captured through the standard deviation (STD), which remains above 5 minutes for all STARs. This level of variation is considerable, given that the average STAR transit time is approximately 20 minutes. Since

aircraft following STAR procedures must adhere to predefined speed and altitude constraints, this high variability is likely attributable to lateral trajectory modifications. These deviations, introduced by ATC vectoring, contribute to substantial differences in flight durations, emphasizing the dynamic nature of arrival management.

The most notable finding is that the optimized travel times generated by our methodology are consistently lower than the baseline travel times. This indicates that the proposed vectoring approach successfully reduces flight durations across all STARs. Specifically, the overall mean travel time decreased from 24.12 minutes (baseline) to 22.97 minutes (optimized travel time). While this reduction may appear modest, its cumulative impact is significant, as evidenced by the total travel time reduction of nearly 4.6 hours, from 5900.25 minutes to 5624.68 minutes across 243 flights. The most substantial time savings were observed in REPOV, where the total travel time decreased by approximately 1.24 hours, demonstrating the efficiency of the proposed vectoring strategy. Similar improvements were recorded in other STARs, such as ARAMA and TOMAN, which also experienced notable reductions in total travel time. Despite these efficiency gains, variability in travel times remains consistent across STARs, as indicated by the STD values, which remain above 5 minutes in all cases. This suggests that while the vectoring strategy effectively reduces flight durations, it maintains a similar degree of fluctuation in travel times. The primary reason for this is that the proposed methodology preserves the original flight sequence, ensuring that flights retain comparable descent phase durations relative to the baseline. As a result, while absolute travel times decrease, the relative variation in transit times remains largely unchanged.

Figure 5: Distribution of Baseline vs. Optimized Travel Time: The histogram compares Baseline (blue) and Optimized (green) Travel Times, with Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) curves showing frequency distributions. A leftward shift in the optimized distribution indicates shorter arrival times, confirming the effectiveness of the methodology in reducing overall flight duration.

To gain deeper insights into the trends observed in travel times, the distribution of baseline vs. optimized travel times is

visualized in Figure 5. The histogram provides a comparative analysis of how travel times are distributed before and after applying the proposed vectoring strategy.

The results indicate that while both the baseline and optimized travel time distributions exhibit similar overall shapes, there is a noticeable leftward shift in the distribution of optimized travel times. This shift suggests a systematic reduction in travel times across most flights, confirming that the proposed vectoring strategy successfully minimizes STAR transit durations. Additionally, the overlapping nature of the two distributions highlights that, despite the reduction in travel time, the general spread and variability of flight durations remain comparable between the two cases. This aligns with the findings that, while travel times are reduced on average, the relative variation in transit times remains consistent due to constraints such as flight separation standards and adherence to speed and altitude restrictions.

Finally, to further investigate the impact of the proposed methodology on individual flight, the scatterplot in Figure 6 provides a comparative analysis of Baseline vs. Optimized Travel Times, where each point represents a flight. Shortcut flights are depicted in blue, while Elongation flights are shown in orange. The black dashed $x = y$ line serves as a reference, indicating where flights would fall if their travel times remained unchanged after optimization. The red regression line highlights the overall trend, demonstrating the impact of the proposed vectoring strategy.

Most data points fall below the $x=y$ line, confirming that the vectoring strategy effectively reduces STAR travel times for the majority of flights. This effect is particularly pronounced for Shortcut flights, which tend to be positioned further below the reference line, indicating greater reductions in travel time. In contrast, Elongation flights are more closely clustered around the $x=y$ line, suggesting that the optimization had a relatively smaller impact on their travel times.

The disparity in optimization impact can be attributed to traffic density constraints. Shortcut vectoring is typically applied in low-traffic conditions, allowing the system greater flexibility to minimize STAR travel times. Conversely, Elongation flights are often constrained by high traffic density, which limits the extent to which travel times can be reduced due to sequencing and separation requirements.

The red regression line exhibits a downward shift, reinforcing the overall reduction in travel times. However, the scatter around the trend line indicates variability in the optimization's impact across different flights. While some flights experience substantial reductions, others show only minor improvements, likely because the optimization model prioritizes system-wide efficiency over individual flight minimization.

A few outliers are observed near or above the $x=y$ line, representing flights where optimized travel times were equal to or slightly longer than baseline values. These cases are most likely due to separation constraints, where maintaining safe spacing took precedence over minimizing travel times.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces an optimization-based sequencing, spacing, and merging methodology to enhance arrival man-

Figure 6: Scatterplot comparing Baseline vs. Optimized Travel Times, with Shortcut flights (blue) and Elongation flights (orange).

agement within high-density Terminal Maneuvering Airspace (TMAs). By automating vectoring operations using simulated annealing optimization, the proposed approach translates historical flight trajectories into structured, conflict-free arrival paths, minimizing flight time while ensuring safe aircraft spacing. The methodology integrates both shortcut and elongation maneuvers, enabling effective sequencing across multiple Standard Terminal Arrival Routes (STARs) and maintaining operational feasibility.

Experimental results confirm that the proposed approach significantly reduces arrival flight times and improves sequencing efficiency. The findings indicate that 95% of flights reach the Initial Approach Fix (IAF) earlier than in the original sequence, while maintaining safe separation. Additionally, the methodology achieves a reduction of over four hours in total arrival flight time in a day of traffic, demonstrating its operational effectiveness in mitigating unnecessary vectoring, reducing congestion, and improving traffic flow management in complex TMAs.

By enhancing predictability and efficiency in arrival sequencing, this work provides a promising framework for integrating automation into ATC decision-making, bridging the gap between tactical ATC interventions and structured ATM systems. Future research can explore real-time implementation of the proposed model, incorporating dynamic airspace constraints and adaptive optimization techniques to further support next-generation air traffic management solutions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research is supported by the National Research Foundation, Singapore, and the Civil Aviation Authority of Singapore, under the Aviation Transformation Programme. Any opinions, findings and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not reflect the views of National Research Foundation, Singapore and the Civil Aviation Authority of Singapore.

- [1] X. Zhu *et al.*, “Predicting aircraft trajectory uncertainties for terminal airspace design evaluation,” *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 2023.
- [2] C. Westin *et al.*, “Building trust in autonomous system competence—the dita digital tower assistant for multiple remote towers, an early concept evaluation,” in *2020 AIAA/IEEE 39th Digital Avionics Systems Conference (DASC)*. IEEE, 2020.
- [3] Z. J. Lim *et al.*, “Towards a greener extended-arrival manager in air traffic control: A heuristic approach for dynamic speed control using machine-learned delay prediction model,” *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 2022.
- [4] —, “A data-driven framework for modelling complexity in terminal manoeuvring area,” in *Proc. 14th EUROCONTROL SESAR Innovation Days*, 2024.
- [5] I. Dhief *et al.*, “Meta-heuristics approach for arrival sequencing and delay absorption through automated vectoring,” in *2023 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*. IEEE, 2023.
- [6] —, “Predicting aircraft landing time in extended-tma using machine learning methods,” in *ICRAT 2020, 9th International Conference for Research in Air Transportation*, 2020.
- [7] H. Jiang *et al.*, “Direct-to initial approach fix: A reinforcement learning approach for conflict-free arrival sequencing in a multi-airport system,” in *Proc. 14th EUROCONTROL SESAR Innovation Days*, 2024.
- [8] I. Dhief *et al.*, “Speed control strategies for e-aman using holding detection-delay prediction model,” in *Proc. 10th EUROCONTROL SESAR Innovation Days*, 2020.
- [9] ICAO, *Continuous descent operations (cdo) manual*, 2010.
- [10] R. Dalmau *et al.*, “Controlled time of arrival windows for already initiated energy-neutral continuous descent operations,” *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 2017.
- [11] S. Chen *et al.*, “How airports enhance the environmental sustainability of operations: A critical review from the perspective of operations research,” *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 2024.
- [12] D. Gui *et al.*, “Optimal aircraft arrival scheduling with continuous descent operations in busy terminal maneuvering areas,” *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 2023.
- [13] T. Polishchuk *et al.*, “How to achieve cdos for all aircraft: Automated separation in tmas-enabling flexible entry times and accounting for wake turbulence categories,” in *Proceeding of 10th SESAR Innovation Days*, 2020.
- [14] R. Sáez *et al.*, “Automated sequencing and merging with dynamic aircraft arrival routes and speed management for continuous descent operations,” *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 2021.
- [15] Y. Zhang *et al.*, “A study of tma aircraft conflict-free routing and operation: With mixed integer linear programming, multi-agent path finding, and metaheuristic-based neighborhood search,” *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2024.
- [16] L. Boursier *et al.*, “Merging arrival flows without heading instructions,” in *7th USA/Europe air traffic management R&D seminar*, 2007.
- [17] M. Liang *et al.*, “Conflict-free arrival and departure trajectory planning for parallel runway with advanced point-merge system,” *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 2018.
- [18] K. Dönmez *et al.*, “Air traffic management in parallel-point merge systems under wind uncertainties,” *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 2022.
- [19] R. Sáez *et al.*, “Traffic synchronization in terminal airspace to enable continuous descent operations in trombone sequencing and merging procedures: An implementation study for frankfurt airport,” *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 2020.
- [20] EUROCONTROL, *User manual for the base of aircraft data (BADA)*, revision 3.6 ed., 2004.
- [21] Civil Aviation Authority of Singapore (CAAS), *Aeronautical Information Publication*, 2024.
- [22] S. Jung *et al.*, “A data-driven air traffic sequencing model based on pairwise preference learning,” *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2018.